

Fabrication of a Pedal-Operated Reciprocating Pump

Moinul Ahsan¹
Md. Shaddam Ibne Khan²
Aminul Islam Mishuk¹

Abstract: People in Bangladesh use diesel engines or electric motor-operated centrifugal pumps for irrigation purposes. But at the root level, farmers have to face a lot of problems in these irrigation processes. Farmers need to maintain diesel engines, which are very expensive. On the other hand, people who use water pumps face the problem of power cuts. The aim of this project is to fabricate a reciprocating pump that can be operated either by an electric motor or pedal so that farmers can continue irrigation during power cuts.

Keywords: Centrifugal pump, Irrigation, Reciprocating Pump.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since diesel prices are rising, farmers are finding it difficult to irrigate their land using shallow machinery during the monsoon. In such a situation, load shedding has become worse. They are worried about irrigation. Frequent load-shedding of electricity and shortage of water for irrigation in intense heat have disrupted public life (1). Making irrigation simpler is the primary goal of creating a pedal-operated reciprocating pump. It can be operated by anyone without access to electricity by a pedal; however, those with electricity can also use an electric motor to run it. While utilizing an electric motor for irrigation is more economical, employing a pedal-operated pump may also be healthier.

2. COMPONENTS AND MATERIALS

Basically there are four main elements required to fabricate pedal-operated reciprocating pump. These elements are:

2.1 Reciprocating pump (i.e. tube-well): Tube well is prepared mainly with five components. The components are:

2.1.1 Metallic tube of cylindrical shape: The main structure of tube well is standing on a metallic cylindrical tube which is made of steel. It is 285 mm long and its thickness is 6 mm. The diameter of the cylinder is 90 mm. A hole is made for outlet of water.

¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Textile Engineering, University of South Asia

² Lecturer, Department of Textile Engineering, University of South Asia

- 2.1.2 Handle: Handle is one of the main components of tube-well. It makes the role of creating pressure of sucking water and works as a connecting rod which is connected with crank. Handle length may increase to achieve greater torque. In this pump a handle of 370 mm is used with the tube well.
- 2.1.3 Bucket: Bucket is usually made of rubber which helps to carry water to the outlet of the tube well. The bucket is attached with a plunger which makes contact with the tube well handle. It works as a piston in the cylinder.
- 2.1.4 Check valve: Check valve is a circular component usually made of rubber and leather. In this pump a check valve of 90 mm is used. When water is sucked from the ground or any other water sources it opens, and when suction stops, check valve close the pipe and create a vacuum pressure. This pressure helps to make water steady before the suction started.
- 2.1.5 Pipe: A pipe is used to bring water from the ground water level or any other water sources like canal, river, water supply line etc. A pipe of 40 mm diameter is used in the pump. That means a hole of 40 mm diameter is occurring in the bottom side of the tube well.
- 2.2 Mechanism of converting rotational movement into reciprocal movement (i.e. crank and connecting rod mechanism): Mechanism of converting rotational movement into reciprocal movement is made by 3 main components. These components are:
- 2.2.1 Crank with pedals: A metallic wheel of 220 mm diameter and of 20 mm thickness is used in this pump. A rod is placed 135 mm away from the center of the wheel to join the connecting rod. For balancing purpose some small amount of weight is also attached with the rod. When the paddle moves rotationally by the human leg it rotates the wheel and then the wheel works as a crank.
- 2.2.2 Connecting rod: A connecting rod of 290 mm is used in the pump. However, the working length (length between two joints) is 240 mm.
- 2.2.3 Pulley: A pulley is attached with the crank. The pulley helps to run the pump with an electric motor by belt pulley mechanism. A rubber belt rounded cross-section is needed to connect the pulley with the electric motor. The diameter of the pulley is 45 mm & thickness is 13 mm.
- 2.3 Casing (i.e. Metallic Frame): The whole system has taken place on a casing or frame. The frame is prepared by 40 mm angle bar. 4 angle bars are used in preparing the frame. The length of the frame is 620 mm, width is 120 mm and thickness is 35 mm. The angle bars that hold the crank and corresponding arrangement is 460 mm is height.
- 2.4 Electric Motor: An electric motor of 150 Watt power will be required to operate this pump with electricity.

3. WORKING PRINCIPLES

When user rotates the paddle by using leg, it gives crank a rotary motion. The crank is connected with the tube-well through a connecting rod. Crank-connecting rod mechanism (2) converts rotary motion into reciprocating motion which reciprocates the handle of the tube-well. There is a joint between the handle and the bucket by plunger. So the handle reciprocally moves the bucket and induced pressure to open the check valve and thus it sucks water through pipe. The system can suck water from 20 feet deep. However, when electric motor is used it rotates the pulley by taper rubber belt using belt-pulley mechanism (3) which is jointed with the wheel. Then the wheel does its job explained above.

In this way this pump works manually and electrically according to need of the users.

4. APPLICATION

The actual design of the pedal-operated reciprocating pump is given below:

Fig 2: Actual Design of the Pump

5. RESULT

Pedal-operated reciprocating pump has been fabricated with locally available components with the help of light engineering works. It was a prototype which fabrication cost was very less. However the water discharge report was encouraging.

Table 1: Test Result

Water Discharge (ml)	130	300	600	840	1050	1420
Time (Sec)	10	20	30	40	50	60

5.1 **Advantages:** The advantages are given bellow:

- It reduces the laborious work
- Irrigation can be done manually and electrically
- Load shedding does not hamper irrigation process
- Does not need to buy diesel or any other petroleum oil
- It can be operate like bicycling that is making the irrigation process so easier which also give health benefit.
- The pump or tube well, the movement converting mechanism and pedal all are attached in a single frame. This makes the entire system moveable.

5.2 **Disadvantages:** The disadvantages are given bellow:

- High-speed electric motor (i.e. 1600 rpm and above) creates less torque. So, the rpm of the electric motor should be controlled to run this pump.
- It creates high noise during operation
- This pump is made of mild steel. So, it should be painted to avoided rust.

6. CONCLUSION

Making of the pedal-operated reciprocating pump might look easy but it was never an easy task. However the pump has been made successfully which will make the irrigation process easier. Definitely root level user will be benefited from it. In future this pump will be more efficient, cheaper, more reliable and more compatible with the help of modern engineering.

REFERENCES

1. **Shamiran Biswas.** Frequent load shedding, a threat to agriculture. *Daily Observer*. [Online] June 9, 2023. <https://www.observerbd.com/news.php?id=423118>.
2. Crank and connecting rod mechanism. *KU Leuven*. [Online] November 22, 2018. <https://www.mech.kuleuven.be/en/tme/thermotechnisch-instituut/basisprincipes/crank-mechanism>.
3. **V. Ryan.** PULLEY SYSTEMS - 1. *Technologystudent.com*. [Online] 2017. https://technologystudent.com/gears1/pulley1.htm#google_vignette.